

Optimisation of burnable absorber particle distribution for reactivity excess compensation in small HTGRs

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ABSTRACT

Passive safety against control rod ejection accidents must be ensured in next-generation small modular reactors (SMRs). This work presents a burnable absorber design approach based on a two-batch distribution of spherical gadolinium oxide particles to achieve precise reactivity excess compensation throughout the fuel cycle of High-Temperature Gas-Cooled Reactors (HTGRs). An automated optimisation framework is developed to determine the optimal radius and number of particles per batch. The methodology couples a surrogate model for multiplication factor evolution, constructed using Sparse Identification of Nonlinear Dynamics (SINDy), with a Differential Evolution genetic algorithm for parameter optimisation. The framework is first tested on a simplified unit-cell model, yielding a particle configuration that maintains reactivity excess below 1\$ for the majority of the burnup cycle. Its robustness is then verified with multiple optimisation rounds, ensuring consistent identification of the optimal set. The binary mixture approach is subsequently applied to a full-core HTGR model, demonstrating its effectiveness in reactivity excess compensation also for more complex systems.

Keywords: High-temperature gas-cooled reactor, control rod ejection, burnable absorbers, surrogate model, design optimisation.

1. INTRODUCTION

High-temperature gas-cooled reactors (HTGRs) represent a promising option for next-generation small modular reactors and offer a potential solution for decarbonising energy-intensive sectors such as maritime transport. A key design objective for HTGRs is **inherent safety**, hence the capability to withstand accident scenarios *passively*, without reliance on active safety systems.

Control rod ejection is among the design-basis accidents that must be addressed throughout reactor operation. When control rods compensate for a significant reactivity excess, their sudden ejection can result in a large positive reactivity insertion. To enhance reactor resilience against such events, the reactivity excess must be minimised throughout the burnup cycle, thereby reducing the required control rod worth. This can be achieved through the use of **burnable absorbers** specifically designed to deplete at a rate that compensates for the decrease in reactivity over the fuel cycle [1].

This work presents a systematic approach to burnable absorber design for HTGRs, including geometry and material selection, as well as requirements for achieving an accurate depletion profile. An automated **optimisation** methodology is developed, combining a genetic algorithm with a surrogate model for neutronics calculations. Neutron transport and depletion analyses are performed using the Serpent Monte Carlo code [2]. *Sparse Identification of Nonlinear Dynamics* (SINDy) [3] is employed to construct a parametrised dynamic model for the multiplication factor, while a *Differential Evolution* algorithm [4] is used to determine the optimal particle configuration in a representative simplified system.

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2. METHODOLOGY

Designing burnable absorbers to compensate for reactivity excess at any time during burnup requires choosing materials, geometry, and distribution of the absorber in order to obtain the desired absorption profile. The criterion used in this work to select each of the characteristics of the absorbers is based on maximising the ease of modulation of the absorption profile.

2.1. Geometry of absorbers

The concentration C_{BA} (cm^{-3}) of a *uniformly distributed* burnable absorber subjected to neutron irradiation decreases exponentially with time as

$$C_{BA}(t) = C_{BA}(0)e^{-\sigma_a^{BA} \int_0^t \phi(t')dt'}, \quad (1)$$

where σ_a^{BA} is the one-group microscopic absorption cross-section of the burnable poison, and the integral of the neutron flux represents the neutron fluence up to time t [5].

Equation 1 indicates that the depletion speed of a uniformly distributed burnable poison depends solely on its absorption characteristics and initial concentration in the system. Consequently, uniformly distributed absorbers are not well-suited for achieving a finely-tuned absorption profile. To enable better control over depletion characteristics, we can exploit the spatial and energy *self-shielding effects* of lumped neutron absorbers. From a geometric perspective, maximising the self-shielding effect requires maximising the absorber volume while minimising the surface area exposed to the neutron flux. With its minimum surface-to-volume ratio, the spherical geometry satisfies this requirement.

A qualitative understanding of the behaviour of **spherical absorbers** under neutron irradiation can be obtained from black absorber particle theory, which provides an analytical expression for the evolution of the macroscopic absorption cross-section Σ_a of spherical particles in time [6]. The latter denotes the probability of absorption per unit length along the neutron path. The formulation reads:

$$\Sigma_a(t) = \pi R^2 N_p \left[1 - \frac{\int_0^t \phi(t')dt'}{4N_0 R} \right]^2, \quad (2)$$

where N_p is particle density, R is their radius, and N_0 is the initial atomic number density of the absorber isotope.

Equation (2) is derived under the following assumptions:

- The absorber particles are “**black**” to thermal neutrons, implying that the neutron mean free path is much smaller than the particle dimensions and that neutron absorption dominates over scattering within the particles.
- The absorber particles are homogeneously dispersed throughout the fuel.
- Neutron scattering in the surrounding medium is weakly anisotropic, and the diffusion length in the medium is much larger than the particle radius.

These assumptions are restrictive, and the black absorber approximation becomes progressively less valid during irradiation. As depletion proceeds, the particles become increasingly transparent to neutrons, reducing the self-shielding effect and causing the depletion profile to change. Nevertheless, for highly neutron-absorbing materials that more closely approximate black absorbers, Equation 2 can provide useful qualitative insights into how the particle depletion proceeds [7].

First, Equation 2 indicates that lumping the absorber into spherical particles introduces additional design parameters—namely, the number of particles per unit volume and their radius—which can be used to tune the depletion rate. Another useful consideration can be derived by assuming, for simplicity, constant neutron flux: in this case, $\Sigma_a(t)$ exhibits a quadratic decrease with time. This implies

that a single batch of particles with uniform radius cannot effectively compensate for reactivity excess throughout the burnup cycle, and that an optimised design will require a mixture of particle populations with different radii and particle loadings. In the present work, a configuration with two particle batches is utilised and tested for reactivity compensation: one batch, composed of smaller particles, to compensate for the higher initial reactivity excess, and another one of larger particles to address the reactivity excess during the latter portion of the fuel cycle.

2.2. Absorber materials

The adoption of multiple batches of spherical particles can, in principle, enable more precise control over the depletion profile, provided that the particles exhibit sufficient self-shielding (i.e., are sufficiently "black" to neutrons). If the **self-shielding effect** is weak, the depletion behaviour approaches that of a uniformly mixed burnable poison, negating the benefits of the spherical geometry. This requirement limits the choice of burnable absorber materials to those with high neutron absorption properties.

Commonly employed absorbing isotopes in nuclear applications include Boron-10, Erbium-167, Europium-151, and Gadolinium-155 and -157. The corresponding materials used for the absorbers are B_4C , Er_2O_3 , Eu_2O_3 , and Gd_2O_3 , respectively. The neutron absorption properties of these isotopes are quantified by their microscopic absorption cross-sections, σ_a [5], which are plotted together in Figure 1, together with the fission cross-section of Uranium-235, for comparison.

Figure 1. Microscopic absorption cross-sections of Gadolinium-155 and -157, Boron-10, Europium-151 and Erbium-167, from 10^{-3} eV to 1 eV. For comparison, the fission cross-section of Uranium-235 is also plotted as a dashed line. The image has been plotted with data from the ENDF/B-VIII.0 library.

For neutron energies below 0.1 eV, σ_a maintains the expected $1/v$ behaviour [5] for all isotopes. Both Europium-151 and Erbium-167 exhibit prominent absorption resonance peaks at approximately 0.5 eV, suggesting potential utility for improving the negative temperature coefficient of reactivity through Doppler broadening effects. However, in the thermal energy range of interest (around 0.1 eV), the two gadolinium isotopes exhibit significantly higher absorption cross-sections, making them more suitable candidates for maximising the self-shielding effect in absorber particles.

To visualise how the absorption properties of the isotopes under consideration influence the self-shielding effect, the evolution of isotopic number density as a function of radial position within the particles can be examined. A simple unit cell containing a single absorber particle embedded in a graphite-fuel medium is modelled using the *Serpent Monte Carlo* code [2]. The particle, with a radius of 0.8 mm, is subdivided into concentric radial zones to accurately track spatial variations in isotopic depletion. Figure 2 presents this spatial depletion behaviour for the two isotopes with the highest and lowest thermal cross-section, respectively: Gadolinium-157 and Erbium-167.

For Gadolinium-157, the outer layer depletes significantly faster than the inner layers, and the change

Figure 2. Atomic density decrement during burnup for the innermost and outermost zones, and for shells 3, 5, 7, and 9 of, respectively, a Gadolinium-157 particle (a) and an Erbium-167 particle (b). The unit cell total heating power is normalised to 27 W in Serpent to simulate a burnup cycle of approximately 6 years. The fuel inventory corresponds to approximately 260 TRISO particles, each with a 350 μm uranium oxide kernel at 17% enrichment.

in depletion rate from one radial position to another is evident. Two distinct depletion regimes can be identified: the outermost layer exhibits an approximately exponential decrease in number density over time, close to the behaviour expected for a uniformly mixed absorber described by Equation (1). In contrast, the inner zones initially deplete at a substantially lower rate, only transitioning to an outer-layer-like depletion later during burnup, when transparency of the outer layers to neutrons increases. This progression highlights how the self-shielding effect affects the absorption profile. On the other hand, Erbium-167, being a weaker absorber, exhibits significantly less pronounced radial variation in depletion rate. The reduced self-shielding effect results in a more uniform depletion profile across the particle radius. If compared to Erbium-167, Boron-10 and Europium-151 present a more evident difference in radial depletion rate, but not as marked as for the two gadolinium isotopes. In this work, we therefore utilise gadolinium oxide as the material for the absorber particles, with gadolinium composed in equal parts (same number density) of its isotopes 155 and 157.

2.3. Optimisation of particle distribution

To evaluate the effectiveness of the binary mixture of particles, a representative simplified system is modelled in Serpent. Figure 3 depicts the **unit cell**, consisting of a fuel compact surrounded by graphite moderator and helium coolant with periodic boundary conditions. The fuel compact has a 30% packing fraction of TRISO fuel particles (i.e. approximately 50000 particles per pin), and the absorber particles are homogeneously mixed with them. This simplified geometry enables the generation of the needed infinite multiplication factor evolution data during burnup.

Since the optimal two-batch configuration depends on four design parameters—the number of particles and radius for each batch—direct manual optimisation utilising Serpent would be prohibitively expensive. Instead, an automated optimisation framework is developed, coupling a surrogate model with a genetic algorithm. The optimization procedure, illustrated schematically in Figure 4, consists of the following steps:

Training data generation. In an early optimisation attempt, a direct automated coupling of the Differential Evolution algorithm with Serpent proved too computationally expensive. Approximately 130 depletion calculations proved vastly insufficient to reach convergence. These calculations, spanning the physically constrained parameter space $\mu = [R_1, R_2, N_1, N_2]^T$, are repurposed as training data for the construction of the surrogate model. For each parameter combination, the evolution of k_∞ with

Figure 3. Simplified single-cell model used to test the optimisation framework. The model is composed of a single fuel compact with TRISO particles in the centre, surrounded by graphite, in beige, and helium, in blue.

burnup is extracted, with initial transient effects due to fission product accumulation removed. The extremes (min; max) for each of the four parameters are, respectively: $R_1 = [0.0102; 0.0400]$, $R_2 = [0.0408; 0.0843]$, $N_1 = [205; 497]$, $N_2 = [103; 299]$.

Surrogate model construction. The burnup trajectories are used to train a parametrised dynamic model using Sparse Identification of Nonlinear Dynamics [3]. The model takes the form of an ordinary differential equation:

$$\frac{dk}{dt} = f(k, \boldsymbol{\mu}, t), \quad (3)$$

where k is the multiplication factor, $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ contains the four design parameters, and time t is included explicitly to prevent the ODE from being autonomous, allowing for non-monotonic behaviour of the solution. SINDy approximates the right-hand side as:

$$f(k, \boldsymbol{\mu}, t) = \Theta(k, \boldsymbol{\mu}, t)\boldsymbol{\zeta}, \quad (4)$$

where Θ is a library of candidate basis functions (a row vector, in this case) and $\boldsymbol{\zeta}$ is a sparse coefficient vector determined by regression. Additionally, a simple polynomial regression model (degree 3) is sufficient to predict the initial condition $k_0(\boldsymbol{\mu})$.

A more detailed treatment of our application of SINDy to the physics of HTGRs is presented in a companion paper at this conference [8].

Optimization. A Differential Evolution algorithm [4] is used to minimise an objective function J quantifying the deviation between the predicted $k_\infty(t)$ trajectory and a target reactivity profile:

$$J = \sum_{i=1}^T w_i (\rho_i - \rho_{\text{goal}})^2, \quad \text{where } w_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \rho_i \geq 0 \\ \alpha & \text{if } \rho_i < 0 \end{cases}. \quad (5)$$

The penalty α is imposed to ensure the optimised profile approaches the target from above (i.e. positive values of ρ_i). The reactivity ρ_i at each burnup step is computed as $\rho_i = (k_i - k_{\text{goal},i}) / (k_i \cdot k_{\text{goal},i}) \times 10^5$ [pcm], where $k_{\text{goal},i}$ is the target multiplication factor at burnup step i . For the simplified unit-cell system, the target reactivity ρ_{goal} is set to zero (i.e. no deviation from k_{goal}), and k_{goal} is set constant and equal to 1.13, to account for the absence of neutron leakage.

For each candidate parameter set, the surrogate model provides a rapid evaluation of the objective function and thus enables an efficient exploration of the design space. Figure 4 provides a schematic representation of the optimisation procedure.

Validation. The optimised parameter set is used to run a full Serpent calculation, to evaluate the accuracy of the surrogate-based optimisation.

Figure 4. Optimisation workflow coupling the SINDy surrogate model with Differential Evolution. Given a set of candidate parameters, the burnup profile is derived by integration of the surrogate model, starting from the predicted initial condition. After each generation of candidate parameter sets, the DE algorithm determines how to evolve them. The loop continues until the maximum number of iterations is reached.

3. RESULTS

This Section outlines the results obtained by addressing three questions:

- Q.1** Can the optimised binary mixture of particles effectively compensate for reactivity excess and maintain a flat multiplication factor profile throughout burnup?
- Q.2** Is the coupled surrogate model-genetic algorithm framework robust and capable of consistently converging to optimal parameter sets?
- Q.3** Can the two-batch configuration be successfully applied to a realistic **full-core** geometry?

Q1. The optimisation routine simultaneously evaluates both the effectiveness of the two-batch particle distribution and the performance of the framework itself. Figure 5 presents results from a single optimisation run consisting of 35 Differential Evolution generations, for a total of approximately 2000 surrogate model evaluations, with a resulting optimal parameter set $\mu = [0.034312 \text{ (cm)}, 0.074678 \text{ (cm)}, 399, 259]$.

Figure 5. Comparison of k_{∞} of the unit-cell system without the absorber particles and with the optimal two-batch distribution found by the optimisation framework, together with the validation trajectory from Serpent.

The penalty factor α for values of k_{∞} below the goal is set to 100, and it is applied only up to approximately 5.5 years along the burnup (evaluated from the k_{∞} profile without burnable absorbers), excluding the end-of-life portion of the fuel cycle (clearly below k_{goal}). The framework accurately predicts the multiplication factor evolution for most of the cycle, though a decrease in accuracy is observed towards the end-of-life. This deviation is attributed to sparse sampling in the upper portion of the second batch particle radius—the parameter influencing the most the late-cycle behaviour—resulting in insufficient

training data for the surrogate model in that region. Nevertheless, Serpent validation of the optimised configuration confirms satisfactory performance, flattening the deviation from the target well below 1\$ (corresponding to about 700 pcm) throughout most of the fuel cycle.

Q2. To assess the framework's robustness, multiple optimisation runs were performed with varying parameter space bounds. The Differential Evolution algorithm consistently converged to similar optimal parameter sets across all runs, demonstrating reliable convergence behaviour. The framework's versatility is also demonstrated by testing on different input k_{∞} profiles. Figure 6 shows the result of the optimisation towards a specific k_{∞} profile with an evident reactivity swing. In this case, α is set to 1 (no penalty for trajectories below the goal). The close agreement between the target profile, the optimised surrogate prediction, and Serpent validation confirms the framework's capability to optimise for diverse reactivity evolution profiles.

Figure 6. Comparison between the k_{goal} profile given as input to the optimisation framework, the resulting optimal trajectory found and the validation profile from Serpent.

Q3. Finally, the two-batch approach is applied to a realistic full-core configuration based on a modified version of the small HTGR design described by Ding et al. [9], with a reduced number of fuel compacts. Figure 7 presents the multiplication factor evolution obtained with Serpent for the full-core system, after manual tuning of the optimised gadolinium oxide particle distribution, resulting in an optimal $\mu = [0.025 (cm), 0.062 (cm), 500, 350]$. The two-batch configuration successfully compensates for reactivity excess in the full-core geometry, though a burnup penalty is observed compared to the unit cell case. This phenomenon, while consistent with findings in other studies [1], requires further investigation.

Figure 7. Burnup with and without the two batches of gadolinium oxide particles for a full-core geometry.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This work demonstrates the effectiveness of a two-batch gadolinium oxide particle distribution for reactivity excess compensation throughout the burnup cycle. An automated optimisation framework was developed, coupling a SINDy-based surrogate model for multiplication factor evolution with a Differential Evolution algorithm for parameter identification. This approach enables thousands of evaluations within minutes, reducing active optimisation time from days to minutes compared to direct manual optimisation with Serpent.

The optimised two-batch configuration successfully maintains reactivity excess below 1\$ for the majority of the fuel cycle in the unit-cell representative system. The framework demonstrates robust convergence behaviour and versatility in achieving diverse target reactivity profiles. Application to a realistic full-core geometry confirms the scalability of the approach, though a burnup penalty due to neutron leakage effects is observed, consistent with literature findings.

Several possibilities for improvement have been identified. First, the unit-cell model should be refined to better represent full-core neutron leakage characteristics, enabling direct transfer of optimised parameters without manual adjustment. Second, more sophisticated sampling strategies could improve surrogate model accuracy with fewer training calculations. A third batch of smaller, quickly depleting particles could be added to deal with the initial remaining deviation from the goal. Finally, the performance of spherical absorber particles in the case of a water ingress accident scenario is currently being investigated and will be addressed in future work.

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